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THE APPLICATION OF AI IN CHEMISTRY EDUCATION

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Annotation: *In today's education system, artificial intelligence technologies, including neural networks, are becoming the main driving force behind digital transformation. The aim of this article is to examine the impact of neural networks on the quality of students' learning in the teaching of chemistry. A comparative pedagogical experiment forms the core methodology of the study. During the study, neural networks were considered as an educational aid, and specific approaches aimed at their effective use by students were described. The study showed that the quality of knowledge was higher when students used neural networks as learning aids. According to the data obtained, AI and neural networks can be effective teaching tools in chemistry education and are recommended for use in the process of educational transformation.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, neural networks, chemistry teaching, quality of knowledge, digital transformation.*

Introduction. Today, the Republic of Kazakhstan attaches particular importance to the transformation of the digital world. As a tangible manifestation of this process, the Head of State, Kassym-Jomart Tokayev, has declared 2026 the 'Year of Digitalisation and Artificial Intelligence'. This initiative is a strategic decision aimed at enhancing the country's technological potential and fostering innovation. Artificial intelligence (AI), which enables computer systems to perform intellectual tasks characteristic of humans, such as data analysis, decision-making, and comparison, is no longer the stuff of science fiction in the 21st century, but is becoming a real tool of everyday life [1; p.1–3]. It is becoming the primary modern applied tool that is transforming the economy, science, medicine, education, and the arts. These digital innovations include machine learning, deep learning, and neural networks [2].

An artificial neural network is an artificial network with a programmed structure that models a biological neuron. The term 'neural network' was originally applied to a network or arrangement of biological neurons [3]. Currently, this term is also used to refer to an artificial neural network. The intensive development of neural networks and their integration into the education system have paved the way for the neural network paradigm. In the modern knowledge system, artificial neural networks are extensively used as a complementary element and a controlling element of the learning process. It is clear that, despite the doubts and scepticism expressed by this group, artificial neural networks have taken educational programmes and processes to a new level. In order to instil public confidence in AI and neural networks, highlight their great potential, and minimise suspicions and misunderstandings, it is necessary to provide clear answers to the following questions:

1. How can AI be used to improve the educational environment?
2. Can we ensure the ethical and equitable application of AI in education? [1; p.12–13].

It can be said that the connection between traditional teaching approaches and innovative digital technologies—a topical issue in the modern educational process—is now evident through the integration of neural networks into subject-specific teaching. The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of neural networks on the quality of students' knowledge of chemistry and to teach students to use neural networks not as a ready-made source of information, but as a supporting tool for the learning process. To achieve this aim, educational resources on AI were analysed, methods for

integrating neural networks into lessons were examined, their strengths and weaknesses were assessed, students were trained in the ethical use of neural networks as a supporting tool, and the results were evaluated.

ChatGPT was chosen as a popular neural network with which most students are familiar, which made its integration easier. It offers features ranging from explanations and practical exercises to the simulation of chemical processes, and adapts to the student's level of proficiency, making learning tailored and effective.

A number of advantages of neural networks:

- Personalisation: neural networks enable the effective processing of large and diverse data by personalising the learning process, taking into account the cognitive characteristics and needs of learners [4; p.18].
- Emotional and social development: develops students' social and emotional skills, making the learning process more adaptive and effective [4; p.19].
- Automated feedback and assessment: neural networks make assessment more objective and effective by analysing students' work, identifying errors, and providing feedback [5].
- Ensuring access to education for people with varying degrees of disability: Neural networks provide individualised support for each student within inclusive education, thereby improving access for students with visual [6], hearing, or mobility impairments [7]. These technologies will enable the identification of gaps in teaching materials and the effective implementation of the principles of inclusive education.

However, the misuse of artificial neural networks by students can lead to the *following drawbacks:*

- Ethical considerations: although neural networks effectively perform data analysis in an educational context, issues of privacy, intellectual property rights, and the reliability of information play an important ethical role. Therefore, digital technologies must ensure ethical data processing and take into account users' subjective interpretations [8; p.25].
- Dependency: reliance on artificial neural networks may lead to a decline in students' individual skills and creative abilities. Regular use is more likely to weaken their ability to calculate, plan, and think independently, and limit their autonomy in the learning process [4; p.35].
- Insufficient understanding of real life: artificial neural networks can make mistakes and produce incorrect phrasing when generating text, which is why they are sometimes referred to as 'stochastic parrots'. As this does not ensure the complete reliability and accuracy of the information obtained via the network, for both learners and teachers, it may cause certain difficulties in the learning process [9].
- Data authors' rights: The data used to train neural networks may be obtained without the authors' permission, which is more likely to infringe their copyright. Furthermore, GPT systems may not comply with European Union data protection requirements without ensuring the right to erasure of personal data, which creates legal and ethical issues for students and teachers [10].

The integration of neural networks into the learning process necessitates the establishment of clear rules and restrictions on their use, taking into account both the positive and negative implications for learners and educators. At the 41st UNESCO General Conference, held from 9 to 24 November 2021 in Paris, the impact of AI on society, human safety, and the environment was discussed, and on 23 November, the 'Ethical Principles on Artificial Intelligence' were adopted [11]. The document highlights ethical issues surrounding the use of AI, such as inequality, digital threats, discrimination, and the potential to impact human rights. The guidelines aim to ensure the safe and responsible use of AI, based on the principles of respect for human rights, environmental protection, inclusivity, and the building of a just society.

In 2024, UNESCO published the document 'Guidelines on the Use of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Education and Research' [12], based on the 2021 'Recommendations on the Ethical Aspects of Artificial Intelligence'. The document aims to ensure the effective and humane use of generative AI as a support tool for learners, teachers, and researchers. Following a theoretical study

of artificial intelligence and neural networks, the ChatGPT neural network was integrated into the chemistry teaching process, taking into account the main risks and limitations.

Method and materials. The practical study was conducted at the N. Nurmakov Specialised Boarding School with the participation of 10-grade students, divided into two subgroups—an experimental group and a control group. The school environment allowed for continuous monitoring of the students' academic performance, behaviour, and engagement, whilst the division into groups ensured an objective comparison of learning outcomes. A total of four chemistry lessons were conducted, integrating ChatGPT as a tool to support the learning process.

To accurately assess the impact of artificial neural networks on the quality of students' knowledge, pre- and post-tests were administered, along with questionnaires before and after the experiment. The students were given instructions on the ethical and effective use of neural networks. According to the results of the pre-test, the quality of knowledge in chemistry in the control group was 46.67%, whilst in the experimental group, the figure was 42.86%. The results of their entrance test are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Entrance test results

10th «B» grade					
I Subgroup (experimental)			II Subgroup (control)		
Students	Score	Assessment	Students	Score	Assessment
1 st student	7	6	1 st student	7	6
2 nd student	5	4	2 nd student	9	8
3 rd student	6	5	3 rd student	6	5
4 th student	6	5	4 th student	9	8
5 th student	11	9	5 th student	11	9
6 th student	7	6	6 th student	7	6
7 th student	10	8	7 th student	6	5
8 th student	6	5	8 th student	7	6
9 th student	3	3	9 th student	7	6
10 th student	9	8	10 th student	5	4
11 th student	6	5	11 th student	7	6
12 th student	10	8	12 th student	12	10
13 th student	11	9	13 th student	8	7
14 th student	11	9	14 th student	8	7
			15 th student	9	8
Average value	7,7	6,4		7,9	6,7
Knowledge qualities	42,86 %			46,67%	

In the experimental group, ChatGPT was used at various stages of the lesson. At the start of the lesson, the neural network generated short review questions to assess students' understanding of the previous material. During independent work, students analysed their answers using the neural network, strictly following the instructions, which helped to develop their analytical and critical thinking skills. At the end of the lesson, the tool was used to monitor progress and identify topics requiring further study.

In addition to academic outcomes, pupils developed digital literacy, including the ability to assess the reliability of information and adjust prompts to obtain more accurate results. This approach enabled them to perceive artificial intelligence not as a 'shortcut' to ready-made answers, but as a tool for deeper and more informed learning. Final tests showed a 14.28% increase in chemistry knowledge in the experimental group, whilst the control group showed an increase of only 6.66%,

which clearly confirms the positive impact of neural networks. For greater clarity, these data have been plotted in Diagram 1.

Diagram 1. The quality of class knowledge in chemistry

The experiment demonstrated that neural networks not only improve the effectiveness of testing but also boost students' engagement, confidence in their knowledge, and interest in studying complex topics. The results of the final assessment are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Final test results

10th «B» grade					
I Subgroup (experimental)			II Subgroup (control)		
Students	Score	Assessment	Students	Score	Assessment
1 st student	10	6	1 st student	11	7
2 nd student	8	5	2 nd student	14	9
3 rd student	11	7	3 rd student	9	6
4 th student	9	6	4 th student	11	7
5 th student	16	10	5 th student	13	8
6 th student	13	8	6 th student	9	6
7 th student	12	8	7 th student	10	6
8 th student	9	6	8 th student	9	6
9 th student	8	5	9 th student	9	6
10 th student	13	8	10 th student	8	5
11 th student	8	5	11 th student	10	6
12 th student	14	9	12 th student	14	9
13 th student	14	9	13 th student	11	7
14 th student	13	8	14 th student	11	7
			15 th student	13	8
Average value	11,3	7,1		10,8	6,9
Knowledge qualities	57,14 %			53,33 %	

Prior to the start of the experiment, a questionnaire was administered to participants in the study group regarding lessons involving neural networks; the results showed that only 28.57% of students in the entire group expressed an interest in using neural networks, not as a direct source of information, but as a supporting tool. After the experiment, the results showed that the number of

students supporting the use of neural networks as auxiliary tools increased from 28.57% to 62%. The results of this questionnaire are presented in the attached diagram (Diagram 2).

Diagram 2. Results of the questionnaire survey in the experimental class

Conclusion. It should be noted that, when used correctly and thoughtfully, neural networks can significantly enhance the effectiveness of the educational process. They help to increase student engagement, personalise learning, and provide opportunities for a deeper understanding of the material; however, they should under no circumstances replace the teacher. The study revealed that students began to perceive neural networks as a useful tool to support learning, rather than merely a means of obtaining ready-made answers.

The effective application of neural networks requires compliance with ethical and legal standards at the state level, as well as appropriate training for teachers and methodological support. The integration of artificial neural networks into the educational process has proven to be an innovative and effective method that helps to strengthen students' thinking, foster curiosity, and develop independent learning skills.

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